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Popular Financial Report San Donato Milanese

2022

S F I N E T N O C

01.

About the city

02.

Geographic location and population

03.

Education

04.

Services provided

05.

Environmental energy and agriculture

06.

City finances

07.

SDM future, SDGs

08.

Awards

09.

Data sources, contacts and website

The Popular Financial Reporting is the report on the Consolidated Group of the City of San Donato Milanese. A streamlined narrative of the performance of public services, economic reporting, the agricultural sector, the educational proposal, the energy sector, and the environmental impact the latter has. It aims to present a 360-degree presentation of all aspects of this city.

Enrico Mattei

We would like to start our work by spending a few words remembering the remarkable man that shaped San Donato Milanese: Enrico Mattei. This visionary Italian industrialist, founder of ENI (Ente Nazionale Idrocarburi) in SDM in 1953, played a pivotal role in discovering and developing Italy's domestic oil reserves. The impact of the company, celebrating in 2023 70 years of activity, was profound. The town was transformed from a suburb into a dynamic and vibrant hub, thanks to the creation of ENI's modern corporate center, research facilities, and housing for its employees. The company's activities also brought considerable revenue to the municipality, which made possible making investments in infrastructure, education, and social services.

MESSAGE FROM THE MAYOR

In the context of global increasing urbanization, medium-sized cities such as San Donato Milanese play a crucial role in the balance between larger urban centers and rural communities. These cities, often characterized by a population of tens of thousands of people, are the breeding ground for unique challenges and opportunities. Governing an urban center of this size requires a deep understanding of local dynamics and population needs, as well as the ability to respond promptly to the economic, social, environmental, and infrastructural challenges of the present and future.

This university project aims to explore what it means to govern a city through a careful analysis that highlights the challenges and opportunities encountered daily in the administration of the public good. To do so, the study delves into the policies undertaken by the city Institutions of San Donato Milanese, highlighting the strategies used to meet the needs of the community and to plan its future development.

A development that must continue to be inspired by the words and the vision of Enrico Mattei, who by founding the corporate village of Metanopoli – today part of the city’s territory – succeeded in building a district that was both an ‘expression of hope’ and an answer to the challenges of the present and the future.

Francesco Squeri

**Casa per casa,
Strada per strada
Quartiere per quartiere.**

01. ABOUT THE CITY

With a population of 32,100 citizens and 12,8 km squared of land, San Donato Milanese is an Italian Municipality located in the Lombardy region of northern Italy, just a few kilometers southeast of Milan. The land is 100% flat, and the vast majority of its territory is anthropized, nevertheless, it is part of the “Rural Park South Milan”, a large protected rural area located south and south-east of Milan.

Thanks to the strong anthropization of San Donato, and thanks to the fact that it is home to very important companies like ENI, the municipality boasts one of the highest Italian GDPs. In fact, with a GDP of 30,500 euros, is positioned 13th among 8,000 Italian cities concerning the contribution to Italian GDP. This is an extraordinary result considering its small dimension.

Its major, Francesco Squeri, elected in 2022, arrived after a period of recession in San Donato. If the GDP is now very high, up until 2017 it was even higher, and it was comprehended in the top ten national list of the richest Italian municipalities.

01. ABOUT THE CITY

San Donato's coat of arms is inspired by the historic past of the city and is made of a blue shield with two crossed swords and a hilt, to remember the battles which occurred in San Donato.

The silver triangular stripe represents the roof of the ancient Church of Pieve of San Donato.

Under it, a military arm can be found to symbolize monks' actions and to remind that part of San Donato's territory was in the past part of the Municipality of Chiaravalle, where the well-known Abbey can be found and visited.

The five towers which make up the crown on top of the shield, represent the recognition of San Donato as a city, which occurred on the 30th of December 1976 thanks to the President of the Republic Giovanni Leone.

Starting from 2014 the municipality created a new city logo, inspired and in addition to the traditional coat of arms. The new logotype is used in digital contests to symbolize the ongoing changes, technological innovation, and journey of renovation to which the Municipality is committed.

01. ABOUT THE CITY

Population composition

Population analysis and trends

Statistics offered by the municipality site, made in collaboration with ISTAT, found out that most of the people living in San Donato are in their 50s (over five thousand, with a peak of people born in 1964 which were in 2022 58 years old) followed by 40-49 years olds. The oldest person in 2022 was reported to be 110-year-old woman, born in 1912.

For what concerns the distribution, the majority of people live in Via di Vittorio (almost 4500) followed by Via Europa (over 1500) and Via Kennedy (almost 1500). The rest of the citizens are divided almost equally in the various streets that don't go over a thousand people each.

Among the 32,100 people living in San Donato, 5531 are students, and 1745 of them are high school students which can find a wide range of fields of study.

Interestingly enough, as a curiosity, the municipality provides also statistics about the most common names used, which in 2022 were found to be Andrea (415) and Maria (339).

01. ABOUT THE CITY

Mission and vision

- 01 Reduction of inequalities**
Intervention on increasing poverty, housing problem, higher bills and pandemic's consequences.
- 02 Investments in society and in sports**
Expand services for fragile people and people with disabilities, with particular focus on the mental health especially for young people. Promoting sport as an occasion for personal and collective growth.
- 03 Protection of green areas**
Defend the territory and the resources from exploitation.
- 04 Promotion of integration and respect**
Intervention in cases of discrimination, promoting hospitality.
- 05 Improvement of parks and public areas**
Urban redevelopment and promotion of cultural events.
- 06 Investment in transportation**
Invest in sustainable mobility, road safety and cycle paths.
- 07 Focus on relationships**
Keep an active listening relationship with the citizens and promote transparency.

02. GEOGRAPHIC LOCATION AND POPULATION

San Donato Milanese is located in the South-Western area of Milan, at 10.9 km from Milan.

Location

Schools

26 schools, between private and public, can be found on the territory.

Municipal libraries, Cascina Roma, Scuola Civica Musica, Danza e Teatro, Cinema Teatro Troisi.

Culture

A new sweet addition to the staff of the Central Library has been made in the early September. The cutest puppy was abandoned twice by his owner, when a random morning he chose his new mum, Roberta. He followed her to the library where she works and became her shadow. They both fell in love. Since that moment, Lucky found a new lovely home and the library a new employee, ready to welcome you and receive cuddles.

Sport

14 sport facilities, including a public pool, a tennis center, athletics tracks and a school of Savate.

Fabio Russo (photo), a San Donato citizen, founded in 2020 the “Ecole de Savate SDM”. The city team won national and international competitions in the past few years, and young athletes got the highest recognition. The most recent has been won by Beatrice Russo (photo), who brought home the belt of the World Cup for Club.

Mr. Russo has also been nominated as the team manager of the Italian sports team of Savate.

Milan Stadium

By 2028 San Donato will host the Milan FC stadium, with around 70 thousands seats.

The urban development project covers an area of 108,000 square meters and includes a modern stadium with a seating capacity of 70,000, as well as hotel, entertainment, and commercial facilities. It is an innovative and ambitious project that aligns with the planned land use for the area. "Caa Icon," a leading international project management and strategic advisory firm, is overseeing the project's implementation, with "Manica," a prominent architectural studio, and entertainment district. The goal of the proposal is to significantly enhance the area through sustainable integrated development, including the creation of a new gateway to Milan in the south and improved connectivity to San Donato, Chiaravalle Abbey, and the parks in the east-west direction. It aims to provide better accessibility and services to the Parco Sud and a well-organized approach to a potential future site. The proposal focuses on creating a unique infrastructure hub in the region, involving railways, metro, and highways, within an already approved Integrated Intervention Plan.

03. EDUCATION

San Donato's municipality offers free access to many different educational paths allowing young people to choose among different options in order to give the most complete range of choice to its citizens.

The "right to study", that San Donato's municipality ensures, is an initiative focused on promoting equal educational opportunities.

The Right to Study Plan, implements interventions and projects that, by supporting the basic school system, aims to ensure equal possibilities for the free access to the right to education and training. The plan performs policy and planning functions around schools, managing the services and interventions designed to ensure the attendance of all children at compulsory school, thereby facilitating the integration of school-age children also to social life, which is essential for harmonious and healthy growth.

Five scholarships are offered to support as many children in their schooling. These grants are intended for students who have finished middle school. To apply, the requirements are: grades of 9 or higher, residence in San Donato, and Isee indicator of less than 20,000 euros.

03. EDUCATION

Activities and services

The Information Desk offers information and initial orientation service on the areas of employment, training, international mobility, local opportunities and youth leadership through the advice of an operator “Informa Giovani” of the Municipality of San Donato Milanese.

This is a free public service and is aimed at young people between the ages of 14 and 35 is responsible for:

- Disseminating information and news regarding various opportunities for study, leisure, work, and volunteering;
- Guide and broaden the possibilities of school and work choices;
- Promote and support youth culture and active citizenship initiatives.

The aim of this is to make young people become active participants in their growth paths and in society and create a space where it is possible to share experiences, interests, ideas, proposals, and projects

The Guidance Desk offers personalized interviews with a professional psychologist to support young people in the decision-making processes in educational and vocational fields.

In addition, territorial events and career guidance in schools are fundamental services that the municipality provides.

04. SERVICES PROVIDED

San Donato Milanese provides citizens with a number of services to overcome every problem and help people in every step of their life.

01

Online services

Online services include the Civil Registry responsible for the registration of citizens after birth, death or migration, the release of IDs and the registration of marriages and civil unions; an office for the Right of Citizenship, offering assistance and consulting services both for Italians and foreigners; the Public Relations office to connect and promote communication between organizational bodies and citizens and an office which is focused on granting support to taxpayers for the payment of contributions and taxes.

02

Service for the Environment

The protection and valorization of the environment through strict proceeding and focused actions is a key important point for the city. Actions have been taken in order to save and preserve the vegetation, animals, water, air, to avoid and reduce pollution and noise.

04. SERVICES PROVIDED

03

Transport and sustainable mobility

Since 2012 there have been different projects to sensitize citizens to environmentally-friendly transportation, proposed by the office for "Mobility". The office is also responsible for the management of public transportation run by ATM, Autoguidovie and Trenord. The centre of Milan is reachable in 14 minutes thanks to San Donato's metro station.

Scooter, car sharing, bike sharing and kilometers of cyclo paths are also available. Additional services are offered to those choosing to move by bicycle: on top of 130 bike parking columns (photo), a bicycle station and a coffee bar offering reparations have been created.

San Donato Milanese also participated in the European Mobility Week to promote more sustainable lifestyles and mobility.

04. SERVICES PROVIDED

04 Welfare and social initiatives

In the city, the social service is active and provides assistance for adults and an anti-violence center for women, services for the elderly (home assistance, day centers, leisure activities, family houses), for disabled people (integration in schools, educational and day centers, individual projects, transportation service, assistance in the world of work and career guidance) and families (protection for minors).

Two of the main goals of the Administration are being transparent and including citizens allowing them to make suggestions and proposals to make the city a better place. For this purpose, the “Vi.Vo” project has been activated after the health crisis to spread solidarity and introduce citizens to the different services and since 2015, 10 collaboration agreements have been created for the urban cure and revitalization.

One of the latest collaborations, signed in December 2021, led to the creation and installation in the pond of a wood artwork called the “Dragone of Metanopoli”, representing both the dragon Tarantasio, Lombard mythological creature, and the iconic 6-paws dog symbol of the company ENI, founded in San Donato (<https://fb.watch/nK8Z0d8P9w/>).

<https://fb.watch/nK8Z0d8P9w/>

04. SERVICES PROVIDED

05

Hospital - Gruppo San Donato

Gruppo San Donato is the number 1 hospital group in Italy, a pioneer in multiple research fields that offers excellent clinical and academic programs in addition to diagnosis and treatment in all medical fields.

Their mission is to make tomorrow's healthcare available for everybody providing 90% of their services through the Italian National Health Service (NHS) and to spread the medical know-how to grant access to quality healthcare around the globe.

In particular, The Policlinico San Donato Research Hospital, founded in 1969, is the largest and most renowned Italian center specializing in cardiovascular treatments and delivers one of the highest number of cardiac ablations in the world.

The IRCCS Policlinico San Donato hosts the Faculty of Medicine and Surgery provided by the University of Milan.

In San Donato Milanese, the Research Center, dedicated to the oil and gas industry, can be found. It consists of a cluster of scientific laboratories with a dual purpose of developing innovative technologies for upstream and downstream activities and providing technical support and assistance to any operations. In addition, it is the birthplace of high-impact technologies such as EST - Slurry Technology and there is a specific section dedicated to environmental technologies for soil remediation, particularly with the phytoremediation techniques. The San Donato Milanese Research Center was opened in 1985 in the Bolgiano district, integrating the historic research facilities of Metanopoli into an innovative complex equipped with state-of-the-art scientific instruments. The facility covers 34,000 square meters and employs about 290 people including researchers, technicians, and support staff. Research projects span all aspects of the upstream and downstream segments, with the common goal of reducing risks, advancing technological knowledge, and achieving greater quality, efficiency, and sustainability in processes, plants, and products. These laboratories bring together a multidisciplinary and integrated range of technical and scientific expertise, ranging from geosciences to engineering, chemistry, and materials science.

05. ENERGY

The new Eni HQ

The VI Eni building in Megalopolis, an "ideal city" near Milan envisioned by Enrico Mattei, is nearing completion. This ambitious project, designed by the Italian-American team Nemesis and Morphosis, is a complex known for its bold architectural design. It features three prominent horizontal towers, futuristic bridge connections, a central canyon, and a large photovoltaic park, shaping the Eni Management Center and embodying the future vision of Italy's largest company. These three towers, each with its unique character - Icon Tower (45m), Landmark Tower (31m), and Sky Garden Tower (38m) - stand as impressive and interconnected structures, representing Eni's global connections. Within the 65,000 square meters of floor space, there will be 4,600 modular workstations, complemented by communal areas within a dynamic base adorned with carefully designed artificial hills, providing an inspiring view of the central square. The project, initiated in 2018, places a strong emphasis on cost efficiency across construction, operation, and maintenance, with a focus on energy performance. It incorporates various sustainable features, such as a significant 8,000-square-meter photovoltaic system, solar panels, green roofs, natural ventilation, advanced thermal insulation, rainwater harvesting, and innovative design technologies, all contributing to the pursuit of LEED Gold certification. Remarkably, the building's facade is meticulously fashioned to optimize energy efficiency and interior illumination.

05. ENERGY

The South Milan Agricultural Park

Agricultural land use dominated during the first half of the 20th century, followed by rapid and extensive industrialization in recent decades. In an almost symbolic nod to the area's environmental heritage, the South Milan Agricultural Park, established in 1990, encompasses 5.3 square kilometers of San Donato Milanese's municipal territory and serves multiple purposes. Its creation, due to the agricultural nature of the Milanese region, primarily seeks to achieve two key objectives: safeguarding the landscape, environmental balance of the metropolitan area, and preserving and promoting agricultural activities, offering clean and equipped recreational spaces for citizens. The environmental characteristics of the park area mirror those of the Milanese irrigated plain, with a history of intensive agriculture dating back to the Middle Ages when reclamation efforts began. The South Park covers a total area of around 46,300 hectares, with agricultural use "patched" within the park boundaries, interspersed with approximately 19,000 hectares of urbanized land. Cattle and pig farming are the primary income-producing activities for the South Park and its constituent municipalities, with 305 farms occupying 30 percent of the park's agricultural territories. Cereals are the most prevalent crop in the region (43% of cultivated agricultural land), followed by rice (22%) and grassland (16%). Smaller percentages are devoted to sunflower, soybean, horticulture, arshland, floriculture, nurseries, poplar groves, and woodland areas.

05. ENERGY

Sustainable energy

The municipality of San Donato Milanese, in collaboration with Hera Luce, a prominent national player in the public lighting sector, is embarking on an exciting green lighting revolution. The project involves the replacement of approximately 4,150 lighting fixtures with state-of-the-art LED technology, resulting in an impressive 60% reduction in energy consumption. This initiative aligns with the goals of the European Green Deal and the UN Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development, emphasizing the fusion of technology and environmental sustainability. Moreover, the project incorporates the installation of new air quality sensors throughout the neighborhoods, contributing to enhanced environmental monitoring. These sensors and control units will offer real-time data on air quality, allowing for continuous monitoring of air pollutants. This wealth of information will play a crucial role in safeguarding the community and addressing climate-related challenges. In essence, this project not only aims to make San Donato Milanese a more attractive and livable place but also significantly contributes to environmental conservation by reducing energy consumption by over 60% and preventing the release of 4,000 tons of CO2 into the atmosphere over the next decade. Additionally, it promotes greater safety for residents by upgrading lighting in key areas of the municipality.

06. CITY FINANCES

Disclaimer: The information provided is summarized and represents only selected funds; therefore, it is not in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP)

The Consolidated Financial Statement of San Donato 2022, shows the financial information and economic situation of the city, contained respectively in the Balance Sheet and in the Income Statement, with reference also to the performance of the previous year (2021). Since the Public Administration Group includes a number of entities and societies, these are included in the Financial Statement data uploaded in the municipality's site. With different degrees of participation by the city, the group is composed by: Azienda Comunale Farmacie, Azienda Sociale Sud Est Milano, Agenzia Metropolitana per la Formazione, l'Orientamento e il Lavoro, Cap Holding SPA, Cubi - Culture Biblioteche in Rete, Rocca Brivio Sforza S.r.l. in liquidazione and the municipality, Comune di San Donato Milanese.

	2022	2021
Non current assets	120.049.839,42	120.036.004,68
Current assets	39.153.622,73	37.446.143,15
Equity	130.607.982,01	131.189.058,73
Debts	17.317.086,32	15.767.809,07

In San Donato Milanese, the Research Center, dedicated to the oil and gas industry, can be found. It consists of a cluster of scientific laboratories with a dual purpose of developing innovative technologies for upstream and downstream activities and providing technical support and assistance to any operations. In addition, it is the birthplace of high-impact technologies such as EST - Slurry Technology and there is a specific section dedicated to environmental technologies for soil remediation, particularly with the phytoremediation techniques. The San Donato Milanese Research Center was opened in 1985 in the Bolgiano district, integrating the historic research facilities of Metanopoli into an innovative complex equipped with state-of-the-art scientific instruments. The facility covers 34,000 square meters and employs about 290 people including researchers, technicians, and support staff. Research projects span all aspects of the upstream and downstream segments, with the common goal of reducing risks, advancing technological knowledge, and achieving greater quality, efficiency, and sustainability in processes, plants, and products. These laboratories bring together a multidisciplinary and integrated range of technical and scientific expertise, ranging from geosciences to engineering, chemistry, and materials science.

“THINK GLOBAL, ACT LOCAL”, GSDs

01 San Donato's strategy centers on reducing social and territorial disparities by enhancing green spaces, expanding services, and improving overall quality of life. Their goal is addressing pandemic-related issues, including poverty, housing emergencies, school dropouts, and economic crises, by implementing measures like housing support, small business aid, education improvement, energy efficiency, and community welfare and safety enhancements.

02 Enhancing services for the elderly, disabled, and families is imperative. The city should adopt a collective responsibility for individual disabilities and elderly care, investing in social enterprises, job placement, and facilitating independent living. Recognizing the growing significance of youth mental health is vital. These years have underscored individual vulnerability, emphasizing the need for a more unified and resilient community.

03 The focus should be on prioritizing the Common Good over private interests, curbing urban sprawl, and promoting environmental sustainability. Prudent management of public resources, reduced external consulting expenses, and reinvestment of private project earnings into improving the city's welfare are key principles to be followed.

04 Prioritizing the region's sporting tradition for personal and collective growth is crucial. Simone Biles' remark, "I feel the weight of the world on my shoulders," upon leaving the field, highlights the significance of a sports culture that centers on physical and mental well-being. Expanding city facilities to foster broader sports participation and facilitating integration through informal and amateur events is imperative.

05 Promoting acts of peace, investing in integration and environmental conservation policies are the objectives. The entire community must collectively embrace civil and respectful behavior towards society. Action is needed against all forms of discrimination and gender-based violence, with a focus on integrating foreign communities and preparing to welcome new refugees. Education should emphasize environmental respect and responsible consumption practices, urban decor respect, and the prevention of vandalism.

06 The goal is to foster a sense of ownership and belonging within the city, emphasizing urban experimentation and revitalization. This includes transforming green areas into functional parks, creating more squares, and regenerating urban spaces through cultural and artistic preservation. Ultimately, the aim is to redefine the urban landscape as a space for collective living, rather than merely transit and consumption.

07 Investing in sustainable mobility, road safety, and intercommunal connections is the primary goal. It is essential to enhance awareness of driving risks, boost confidence in public transportation, and promote bicycle culture. The overall parking plan should be supported, with particular modifications to promote pedestrian areas and local commerce. Improvements are needed for safe, continuous, and wheelchair-accessible cycling and pedestrian paths. Action should be taken at all levels to alleviate congestion on the Pallese road with a metropolitan subway line.

08 The relationship with citizens should be continuous and transparent. The goal is for the administration to encourage participation even beyond the electoral deadlines and promote active citizenship practices. As independent civic groups, the commitment is to maintain an active presence in the community, acting as intermediaries for citizens' concerns and fostering a dialectical relationship with the administration, rather than becoming a propaganda tool for it.

08. AWARDS

Awards in the city

“Group San Donato” Hospital, won the best Italian Hospital award in 2022.

It has been awarded with a first prize in the category of private group of excellence and the second prize in the category of “Digital Excellence”.

San Donato boasts on its territory the presence of the largest published street poem ever written in the world. Drawn on an area of 11,248 square meters, 10 meters high on the roof of the soundproofing barrier wall of the station, it's the work of a Sandonatese citizen. The artwork, remaining a provocation, evokes the intrinsic love for the neighborhood, which consists of a one-kilometer dead-end street divided by the rest of the city because of the wall.

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